

Interkingdom signaling dynamics in the cereal holobiont: microbiome-mediated pathways to drought resilience

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ABSTRACT

Root-associated microbiomes are increasingly recognized as important contributors to drought adaptation in cereal crops. Rather than functioning solely through improved nutrient acquisition, beneficial microorganisms can reshape host stress responses by modulating interconnected signaling, metabolic, transcriptional, and epigenetic pathways. Emerging evidence suggests that the plant-microbiome interactions operate through complex interkingdom signaling networks that coordinate root physiology, hormonal regulation, reactive oxygen species homeostasis, and stress-responsive gene expression, ultimately reinforcing drought resilience. However, current understanding of microbiome-mediated drought adaptation remains fragmented across ecological, omics, and molecular signaling perspectives. In this review, we synthesize current knowledge on microbiome-mediated signaling mechanisms underlying drought resilience in cereals from a holobiont-oriented perspective, in which plants and their root-associated microbiomes are viewed as integrated adaptive systems. We discuss how drought-responsive microbiomes influence plant adaptation through genomic and functional complementarity, multi-omics reprogramming, and modulation of core regulatory hubs, including protein kinases, transcription factors, phytohormones, reactive oxygen species, small signaling peptides, miRNAs, lncRNA-associated networks, and epigenetic regulation. Finally, we highlight major mechanistic gaps, technological challenges, and emerging opportunities for microbiome-informed engineering strategies aimed at improving cereal drought resilience.

1. Introduction

Cereal crops are central to global food security but are increasingly threatened by climate change. Rising temperatures, recurrent drought events, and greater climatic variability are progressively pushing

agricultural systems toward more water-limited conditions, substantially constraining cereal productivity and threatening future food demand (Martin-Candilejo et al., 2024; Webber et al., 2018). As drought remains one of the most severe limitations to cereal production, understanding the mechanisms that underpin plant resilience has become

Abbreviations: ABA, abscisic acid; ACC, 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate; AQuS, aquaporins; AMFs, arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi; APX, ascorbate peroxidase; AUX/IAA, auxin; BR, brassinosteroids; CAT, catalase; CEP, C-terminally encoded peptides; CLE, CLAVATA3/Embryo surrounding region-related peptides; CDPKs, Ca²⁺-dependent protein kinases; CIPKs, calcineurin B-like interacting protein kinases; CK, cytokines; ETH, ethylene; DHN, dehydrins; GA, gibberellin; GPX, glutathione peroxidase; GST, glutathione; lncRNAs, Long non-coding RNAs; JA, jasmonic acid; MAPKs, mitogen-activated protein kinases; miRNA, micro RNA; miPEPs, miRNA-encoded peptides; RBOHs, respiratory burst oxidase homologs; RLKs, receptor-like kinases; ROS, reactive oxygen signaling; SL, strigolactones; SnRK2s, sucrose nonfermenting-related kinase 2s; SSPs, small secreted peptides; SOD, superoxide dismutase; SynComs, synthetic microbial communities; TFs, transcription factors.

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an urgent research priority.

Plant adaptation to drought relies on highly coordinated signaling and gene regulatory networks that integrate stress perception with physiological and developmental responses (Fig. 1). Advances in omics technologies have substantially expanded our understanding of drought-responsive genes and signaling pathways (Yang and Qin, 2023; Zhang and Zhang, 2022). However, growing evidence suggests that plant drought adaptation emerges not only from host regulatory responses but also from interactions with root-associated microbial communities (Z. Li et al., 2025).

The rhizosphere functions as a highly interactive interface where plant roots and diverse microbial communities establish dynamic chemical and molecular exchanges (de Vries et al., 2020). Through root exudates and other metabolites, plants selectively recruit microbial partners (Styer et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2021). In turn, root-associated microbiomes can reinforce drought adaptation by modulating host signaling, stress responses, and root physiology, thereby extending the plant's intrinsic adaptive capacity (Lee et al., 2024; Qi et al., 2022; Yue et al., 2024). These interactions increasingly support a holobiont-oriented perspective, in which drought resilience is viewed as an emergent property of integrated plant-microbiome interactions rather than plant responses alone (Elango et al., 2025a). Although beneficial microbial effects on drought tolerance have been widely documented, current understanding remains fragmented across ecological, omics, and molecular signaling perspectives. In particular, a mechanistic synthesis linking microbiome assembly, host regulatory

reprogramming, and drought-responsive signaling pathways in cereals is still lacking.

Here, we synthesize current knowledge on interkingdom signaling within the cereal holobiont, focusing on how drought-responsive microbiomes reshape plant stress adaptation through regulatory mechanisms. We first discuss the root microbiome as an extension of the cereal stress-response system and then examine microbiome-mediated regulation of plant gene expression, epigenetic remodeling, and core signaling hubs, including protein kinases, transcription factors, ROS, and phytohormone signaling, as well as peptide- and RNA-mediated regulatory networks. By integrating multi-omics evidence with mechanistic insights, we highlight emerging opportunities and major knowledge gaps for leveraging microbiome-derived functions to improve drought resilience in cereals. Although this review focuses on cereals, selected findings from model systems, particularly *Arabidopsis thaliana*, are incorporated where they provide broader mechanistic insight.

2. Root microbiome as an extension of the cereal stress-response system

Root-associated microbiomes increasingly appear to contribute to cereal drought resilience through ecological, evolutionary, and functional capabilities that complement plant stress responses. Rather than acting as passive rhizosphere inhabitants, microbial communities can support drought adaptation by shaping ecological interactions, expanding functional capacities, and participating in long-term adaptive

Fig. 1. Overview of drought stress signaling in plants and root microbiome contribution. The plant drought stress response progresses through five key phases: (1) Signal perception: Stress signals are detected by membrane-localized sensors and receptors; (2) Signal transduction: Secondary messengers ROS, Ca²⁺, sugars) relay stress signals intracellularly; (3) Signal amplification: Downstream cascades engage protein kinases, transcription factors (TFs), and phytohormones, which synergize with miRNAs and small peptides to modulate stress responses; (4) Gene regulation: Stress-responsive genes are expressed to initiate adaptive mechanisms; (5) Physiological adaptation: Drought tolerance is achieved through stomatal closure, root elongation, and metabolic reprogramming. The root microbiome enhances these pathways by priming signal perception, modulating secondary messengers, and influencing gene expression.

processes. These complementary dimensions are explored in the following sections.

2.1. Root microbiome as evolutionarily integrated component of cereal drought adaptation

Drought adaptation in cereals increasingly appears to emerge from integrated plant-microbiome interactions rather than plant responses alone. Long-term co-evolution between plants and root-associated microbiomes has generated tightly interconnected biological systems in which plant and microbial genomes influence one another and collectively respond to environmental challenges (Barnes et al., 2024; Cosme, 2023).

Longer-term drought resilience appears to be shaped through reciprocal selection between plants and their associated microbiomes (Lozano et al., 2022; Schmidt et al., 2024). Repeated drought exposure can favor microbial taxa with enhanced stress tolerance and efficient root colonization, while plants simultaneously refine recruitment strategies that enrich beneficial microbial partners (Ginnan et al., 2025; J. Li et al., 2025; Qi et al., 2025). Such reciprocal selection suggests that drought-responsive microbiomes should not be viewed merely as external environmental assemblages, but as evolutionarily embedded partners contributing to adaptive plasticity within the cereal holobiont.

Under drought, root microbiomes often respond more rapidly than host plants, with transcriptional shifts that can precede plant stress responses (Pande et al., 2023; Qi et al., 2025). Drought-driven shifts in microbial population structure, functional selection, and horizontal gene transfer (HGT) may further accelerate microbiome adaptation under drought stress (Zilber-Rosenberg and Rosenberg, 2021). Notably, recent work identified 75 full-length genes exchanged bidirectionally between plants and root-associated bacteria via HGT (Haimlich et al., 2024). Genes transferred from bacteria to plants were enriched in carbohydrate metabolism, whereas genes transferred to bacteria included functions related to auxin biosynthesis, suggesting reciprocal exchange of traits relevant to stress adaptation and host-microbe coordination.

The functional relevance of such exchanges is illustrated by the discovery of a microbial *DET2* homologue involved in BR biosynthesis in drought-alleviating *Actinobacteria* (Haimlich et al., 2024). Expression of this microbial gene in the *Arabidopsis det2* mutant restored normal plant growth, indicating that microbial functions can compensate for disrupted host hormonal pathways. These findings imply that microbial evolutionary processes may directly shape host stress responses by contributing functional traits relevant to signaling and stress adaptation.

2.2. Root microbiome assembly as an ecological extension of cereal stress-response systems

From an ecological perspective, drought reshapes root microbiome assembly through plant-mediated changes in rhizosphere chemistry (Z. Li et al., 2025; Qi et al., 2022). Under water limitation, cereals alter the composition and quantity of root exudates, including hormones, nutrients, and secondary metabolites that function as chemical cues guiding microbial recruitment to the rhizosphere (Balasubramanian et al., 2021; Styer et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2021). Across plant systems, these drought-induced shifts consistently enrich specific microbial taxa, suggesting the existence of conserved ecological filtering processes during water limitation (Gholizadeh et al., 2024).

A hallmark of this restructuring is the recurrent enrichment of drought-responsive microbial groups, particularly members of *Actinobacteria*, including *Streptomyces*, alongside representatives of *Firmicutes* and *Proteobacteria* (Kabir et al., 2025; Wu et al., 2024). Importantly, many of these taxa have been experimentally shown to improve plant performance under drought when tested individually or as synthetic consortia (Z. Li et al., 2025; Rigerte et al., 2025). These findings suggest that drought-induced microbiome shifts do not merely reflect stress-driven community turnover, but rather selective enrichment of

microbial partners with functional relevance to host drought adaptation (Table 1).

Fungal communities (in particular, AMFs) also emerge as recurrent components of drought-responsive root microbiomes and are frequently enriched in cereal roots under drought (Kabir et al., 2025; Swift et al., 2025). In contrast to many bacterial taxa, fungal communities often display greater ecological stability during drought, partly because they appear less sensitive to drought-induced changes in root exudation (Bourceret et al., 2022). Their extensive hyphal networks facilitate water and nutrient acquisition and often remain stable or become more interconnected during drought stress (C. Gao et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2023). They enhance drought tolerance via improved hydraulics, nutrient uptake, photosynthesis, and signaling networks (Table 2). Beyond supporting host performance, AMFs may also stabilize drought-responsive microbiomes by reducing bacterial mortality and buffering desiccation stress within the rhizosphere (Hestrin et al., 2022; Imran et al., 2023). These observations position fungi as ecological stabilizers that help maintain microbiome function under water limitation (Table 2).

From a holobiont perspective, drought-induced shifts in microbiome composition likely represent an adaptive reorganization of the cereal root system, in which plants actively recruit and maintain microbial functions that extend their capacity to cope with environmental stress.

2.3. Root microbiomes as a genomic and functional extension of stress-response systems

Under drought, cereals recruit specialized microbial communities whose genomic and functional repertoires complement plant stress physiology and expand host adaptive capacity. Root-associated microbes harbor diverse genes linked to nutrient mobilization, hormonal regulation, osmoprotection, and stress signaling (Jayakumar et al., 2021; Narayanasamy et al., 2023; Ripa et al., 2019; Robertson-Albertyn et al., 2022). Such functions suggest that microbial genomes may act as functional complements to plant stress-response systems by supplying metabolic, signaling, and regulatory capacities that reinforce drought adaptation.

One major contribution of drought-adapted microbiomes lies in maintaining nutrient acquisition under drought, where nutrient diffusion and plant uptake are often severely constrained. Genomic profiling of barley rhizosphere microbiomes has revealed enrichment of genes involved in nitrogen fixation and phosphate solubilization, processes that directly support host nutritional demands (Robertson-Albertyn et al., 2022). Wheat-associated fungal endophytes also possess genes for phosphate mobilization, siderophore production, and nutrient acquisition pathways that improve mineral availability under drought (Ripa et al., 2019). These microbial functions may therefore compensate for drought-induced limitations in plant nutrient uptake and reinforce host metabolic homeostasis.

Microbial genomic traits also support drought adaptation through osmotic regulation and oxidative stress mitigation. The drought-protective microbe *Bacillus albus* LRS2 produces a wide range of drought-responsive metabolites such as organic acids, osmolytes, antioxidants, and phenolics (Rajkumar et al., 2024). Microbial pathways involved in trehalose biosynthesis and antioxidant production have been linked to improved cellular protection against dehydration and oxidative damage (Ahmad et al., 2025). These microbial functions can reinforce plant antioxidant systems and osmotic adjustment mechanisms, thereby buffering cereals against drought-induced physiological disruption.

In addition to nutritional and metabolic buffering, drought-associated microbes possess genomic traits capable of modulating plant hormonal signaling. Wheat-associated fungal endophytes and bacterial taxa encode genes linked to ACC deaminase activity, IAA biosynthesis, and signaling regulation (Narayanasamy et al., 2023; Ripa et al., 2019). Microbial volatile organic compounds can also contribute

Table 1
Effects of drought-responsive bacterial inoculation on plant gene expression and drought tolerance in cereal crops.

Plant	Microbial Inoculation	Targeted Genes	Genes Function	Reference
<i>Actinobacteria</i> : Actinobacterial strains alone or in combination with other microbes				
Wheat	<i>Streptomyces pactum</i> Act12	<i>EXPA2</i> , <i>EXPA6</i> <i>P5CS</i> <i>SnRK2</i>	Proline biosynthesis ABA signaling	H. Li et al. (2020)
Rice	<i>Streptomyces albidoflavus</i> OsiLf-2	<i>ECTA</i> , <i>ECTB</i> , <i>ECTC</i> , <i>NHX1</i> , <i>HKT1.5</i> <i>LEA3</i> , <i>RAB16A</i> <i>DREB2A</i> <i>ALAD</i> , <i>PSY3</i> , <i>ATPE</i>	Osmotic homeostasis Stress response TF Photosynthesis	Niu et al. (2022)
<i>Firmicutes</i> : <i>Bacillus</i> strains alone or in combination with other microbes				
Maize	A <i>Bacillus</i> consortium	<i>PAL</i> , <i>FSNII</i> global DNA methylation (5-mC) <i>CTR1/DREB2</i>	ROS scavenging Gene expression TF	Lephatsi et al. (2022) Barnawal et al. (2017)
Wheat	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> <i>Bacillus</i> sp. and <i>Paenibacillus beijingsensis</i>	<i>CAT</i> , <i>APX</i> <i>ACO1</i> , <i>ACO2</i> , <i>ACS1</i> <i>DHN3</i> , <i>LEAs</i> <i>PR1-1a</i> <i>NAC2D</i> , <i>NAC35</i>	ROS scavenging ET biosynthesis Stress response SA metabolism TFs	Li et al. (2019)
Millet	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	<i>DREB-1E</i> , <i>ERF-1B</i> , <i>APX1</i> , <i>SOD1</i>	TFs ROS scavenging	Murali et al. (2021)
Rice	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> and <i>Brevibacillus laterosporus</i>	<i>MYB3R-2</i> , <i>DREB1A</i> <i>DIL</i> <i>CDPK13</i>	TFs Lipid transfer Kinase activity	Kakar et al. (2016)
	<i>Bacillus endophyticus</i> PB3, <i>Bacillus altitudinis</i> PB46, and <i>Bacillus megaterium</i> PB50	<i>LEA</i> , <i>HSP70</i> , <i>RAB16B</i> <i>SNAC1</i> , <i>bZIP23</i>	Stress response TFs	Devarajan et al. (2021)
	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> SN13	<i>USP</i> , <i>DEF</i> , <i>CYP450</i> , <i>GST</i> <i>MYB</i> , <i>bZIP</i>	Stress response TFs	Bisht et al. (2025)
	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i> CACC109 and CACC119	<i>CAT</i> , <i>POD</i> , <i>APX</i> , <i>SOD</i> <i>WRKY47</i> , <i>ZIP23</i> , <i>DREB2</i> , <i>NAC066</i> , <i>AREB1</i> , <i>AREB2</i>	ROS scavenging TFs	Lee et al. (2024)
	Different <i>Bacillus</i> sp., <i>Pseudomonas azotoformans</i> , <i>Rhizobium</i> sp., <i>Chryseobacterium</i> sp.	<i>COX1</i> , <i>NRAMP6</i> , <i>GST</i> , <i>DHN</i> <i>AP2/EREPP</i> , <i>GRAM</i> , <i>NAM</i> <i>EXP1</i> , <i>EXP2</i> , <i>EXP3</i>	Stress response TFs Expansins	Omar et al. (2021)
	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i> GH1-13	<i>APX</i> , <i>GPX</i> , <i>CAT</i> , <i>SOD</i> <i>bHLH148</i> , <i>JAMYB</i>	ROS scavenging JA-signaling	Park et al. (2024)
<i>Proteobacteria</i> : <i>Pseudomonas</i> strains alone and in combination with other microbes				
Maize	<i>Pseudomonas putida</i> FBKV2	HSPs, LEAs <i>CYP71C2</i> , <i>CYP71C4</i> <i>ACO</i> , <i>ACS2</i> , <i>AP2/ERFs</i> <i>ABI5</i> , <i>PP2Cs</i> , <i>STPKs</i> <i>AUX/IAA7</i> , <i>GH3.8</i> , <i>GH3</i> , <i>SAUR56</i> <i>SOD</i> , <i>CAT</i> , <i>POD</i>	Response to stress benzoxazinoid biosynthesis ET biosynthesis and signaling ABA signaling AUX signaling ROS scavenging	SkZ et al. (2018)
Rice	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	<i>COX1</i> , <i>HSP20</i> , <i>COC1</i> <i>PKDP</i> <i>bZIP1</i> , <i>AP2/ERF</i>	Response to stress Kinase activity TFs	Saakre et al. (2017)
	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i> and <i>Trichoderma asperellum</i>	<i>PAL</i> , <i>SODs</i> , <i>APX</i> , <i>POD</i> , <i>CAT</i> <i>PiP</i> <i>DREB</i>	ROS scavenging Water hemostasis TFs	Singh et al. (2020)
Other <i>Proteobacteria</i>				
Wheat	<i>Enterobacter bugandensis</i> WRS7	<i>CAT</i> , <i>APX</i> , <i>GPX</i> <i>P5CS</i> , <i>P5CR</i> , <i>TPS1</i> <i>NCED</i> , <i>WZE</i> , <i>SAMS</i> , <i>ACS1</i> , and <i>ACO</i>	ROS scavenging osmolyte synthesis Biosynthesis of phytohormones	Arora et al. (2023)
	<i>Enterobacter</i> sp., <i>Klebsiella</i> sp., and <i>Flavobacterium</i> sp.	<i>TPC1</i> <i>DHNs</i> , <i>CAT1</i> <i>DREB2A</i>	calcium transporter Response to stress TFs	(Gontia-Mishra et al., 2016)
	<i>Rhizobium leguminosarum</i> (LBM1210 and LET4910)	<i>CAT1</i> <i>CYP707A1</i> <i>DREB2</i>	ROS scavenging ABA catabolism TFs	Barquero et al. (2022)
Sorghum	<i>Enterobacter</i> sp., <i>Enterobacter cloacae</i> , <i>Ochrobactrum</i> sp., and <i>Microbacterium</i> sp.	<i>P5CS2</i> , <i>P5CS1</i>	Proline biosynthesis	Govindasamy et al. (2020)
Maize	<i>Azospirillum</i> sp. and <i>Herbaspirillum</i> sp. <i>Ochrobactrum</i> sp.	<i>NCED/ZmVP14</i> <i>ZIP</i> , <i>ABRE</i> , <i>AP2</i> , <i>NAC1/57</i> , <i>NAM</i> , <i>ATAF1/2</i> <i>MLG3</i> , <i>LEA5A</i> , <i>LEA14A</i> <i>APX</i> , <i>GST2</i> <i>ARG</i> , <i>CBF</i> , <i>DBF</i> , <i>DHN1</i> , <i>ERD</i> , <i>CUC2</i>	ABA biosynthesis TFs LEAs ROS scavenging Stress response	Curá et al. (2017) Kumar et al. (2020)
	<i>Mitsuaria</i> sp. and <i>Burkholderia</i> sp.	<i>RAB17</i> , <i>CAT1</i> <i>P5CS1</i> <i>NCED1</i>	Response to stress Proline biosynthesis ABA biosynthesis	Huang et al. (2017)
Millet	<i>Shewanella putrefaciens</i> and <i>Cronobacter dublinensis</i>	<i>NCED</i> , <i>GA20ox</i> , <i>YUC</i> <i>AP2</i> , <i>SNAC1</i> , <i>DREB2A</i> <i>LEA</i> , <i>P5CS</i>	Phytohormone biosynthesis TFs Response to stress	Manjunatha et al. (2022)

Table 2
Fungi-induced gene expression and drought tolerance in cereal crops.

Plant	Microbial Inoculation	Targeted Genes	Genes Function	Reference	
AMF strains alone or in combination with other microbes					
Maize	<i>Rhizophagus irregularis</i>	<i>PIP2.4, TIP1.1</i>	Water homeostasis	Quiroga et al. (2018)	
		<i>Piriformospora indica</i>	Response to stress	Xu et al. (2017)	
	A consortium of AMF and <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	<i>CBL1</i>	Calcium sensor	Armada et al. (2015)	
		<i>DREB2A, ANAC072</i>	TFs		
Wheat	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> ON307213	<i>PIP1.2, PIP2.1, PIP2.2, PIP2.3, PIP2.5, PIP2.6</i>	Aquaporins	W. Zhang et al. (2018)	
		<i>SnRK2s, MYB, NAC, AP2/ERF, Aux/IAA, ARF, TGA1, TGA4</i>	ABA		
		<i>ARR9, ARR2</i>	AUX signaling		
		<i>GSTs, microtubule-associated genes</i>	SA signaling		
	<i>Funneliformis mosseae</i>	<i>NIP1.10, NIP3.3, NIP3.4</i>	Stress response	George et al. (2024)	
		<i>Chaetomium</i> sp.	<i>PP2C-a7, PP2C-a10, PP2C-a30</i>	Proline biosynthesis	Asadollahi et al. (2023)
	<i>SnRK2, MAPK3, MAPK12.1, MAPK16</i>		Aquaporins		
	<i>Mortierella alpine</i>	<i>Piriformospora indica</i>	<i>NAC2, SIM, and bZIP15</i>	Phosphatase activity	Pan et al. (2024)
			<i>CIPK9, PP2C30</i>	Kinase activity	Yue et al. (2024)
	Sorghum	<i>Rhizophagus irregularis</i> and <i>Rhizophagus arabicus</i>	<i>DREBs, AREBs, NCED, ABA2</i>	Phosphatase activity	Ahmad et al. (2025)
<i>PIP1.1, PIP2.2, PIP2.5, PIP2.8, TIP1.1, TIP2.3, NIP1.2, NIP2.2</i>			ABA biosynthesis	Symanczik et al. (2020)	
Endophytic fungi alone or in combination with other microbes					
Rice	<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i> SL2	<i>RBCS, OsRBCS1, RBCS2</i>	Aquaporins	Doni et al. (2019)	
		<i>CAND, MOC1</i>	Photosynthesis		
		<i>PHR2</i>	Molecular functions		
	<i>Trichoderma asperelloides</i> and <i>T. brevicompactum</i>	<i>Trichoderma asperelloides</i> and <i>T. brevicompactum</i>	<i>ARF12, OsGAE1</i>	Nutrient uptake	Quazi et al. (2024)
			<i>CYP38 and CYP20-2</i>	AUX signaling	
			<i>AQU-2, DHN, DREB</i>	GA biosynthesis	

to plant-microbe communication by triggering systemic drought responses and altering endogenous hormone profiles (Kulkarni et al., 2024; Luo et al., 2022; Paul et al., 2022; Yasmin et al., 2021). These findings show that microbial genes can modulate plant stress signaling either directly through phytohormone synthesis, transport, or

perception or indirectly via VOC-mediated communication, enhancing drought responses within a holobiont system.

At the community level, drought resilience emerges from complementary functions distributed across microbial consortia rather than single microbial traits. A barley SynCom composed of members of *Proteobacteria*, *Firmicutes*, and *Actinobacteria* encoded plant-growth-promoting pathways associated with IAA biosynthesis, ACC deaminase activity, and siderophore production (Rigerte et al., 2025). Likewise, a wheat-derived SynCom assembled from drought-tolerant taxa carried genes involved in antioxidant production, trehalose synthesis, IAA biosynthesis, and terpenoid backbone metabolism (Xiang et al., 2025). Together, these findings indicate that microbial consortia function as coordinated systems that expand the cereal drought-response repertoire through distributed metabolic and signaling capacities within the holobiont.

3. OMICs insights into microbiome-mediated drought resilience in cereals

3.1. Metabolic reconfiguration

Metabolomic evidence increasingly indicates that root-associated microbiomes actively reshape plant metabolic responses under drought, particularly pathways linked to osmotic adjustment, antioxidant defense, and carbon metabolism. Drought-responsive bacteria, including *Streptomyces*, *Bacillus*, and *Sphingomonas*, alter the abundance of primary metabolites such as sugars, amino acids, organic acids, and fatty acids that function as osmoprotectants, energy reservoirs, and signaling molecules under water deficit (Bisht et al., 2025; Rajkumar et al., 2024; Shan et al., 2025; F. Wang et al., 2022). Similarly, colonization by *Rhizophagus irregularis* BGC AH01 modifies unsaturated fatty acid metabolism, ornithine cycle intermediates, and the biosynthesis of polyamines and carbohydrates in drought-stressed maize seedlings (Hu et al., 2020).

In parallel, microbiome-mediated metabolic reconfiguration strengthens antioxidant defense through changes in secondary metabolism. Following microbial colonization, cereals differentially regulate flavonoids, phenolics, alkaloids, anthocyanins, carotenoids, and terpenoids (El-Shazoly et al., 2025; Hagaggi and Abdul-Raouf, 2022; Quazi et al., 2024; Tereucán et al., 2021). These metabolites contribute to ROS buffering and cellular protection under dehydration stress.

It is worth noting that metabolomic outcomes often differ between individual strains and microbial consortia. *Streptomyces* consortia induce pronounced shifts in drought-responsive metabolites (Nivedita et al., 2024; Shan et al., 2025), while AMF consortia promote the accumulation of osmolytes, proteins, and antioxidant compounds in maize (Singh et al., 2023). Moreover, different microbial consortia induced distinct metabolomic signatures (Lephatsi et al., 2022; Othibeng et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2023). These findings suggest that microbiome composition influences the mechanisms through which drought resilience is achieved, highlighting the importance of functional complementarity among microbial members during stress adaptation.

3.2. Proteomic remodeling

Beneficial root-associated microbes substantially reshape plant proteomic landscapes under water limitation. These studies show that microbial partners can reprogram protein abundance, turnover, and pathway activation in ways that reinforce drought adaptation across multiple physiological and regulatory levels.

A major consequence of microbiome-mediated proteomic remodeling is the stabilization of core physiological processes disrupted by drought, particularly photosynthesis and cellular stress protection. Beneficial microbes frequently enhance the accumulation of proteins associated with photosynthetic maintenance, amino acid metabolism, molecular chaperoning, and stress defense (Bernardo et al., 2017;

El-daim et al., 2019). One example is *Bacillus velezensis* 5113, which enhances drought tolerance in wheat by increasing proteins associated with photosynthesis, amino acid transport, molecular chaperoning, and stress protection, including Rubisco, HSP16.8, HSP26, and several photosystem-associated proteins (El-daim et al., 2019).

Microbial agents further induce a wide array of changes in the plant's proteome associated with the modulation of phytohormones (e.g., SA, CK, and IAA) and developmental plasticity (Rodríguez-v and Mesa-marín, 2023; Yadav et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022), thereby reshaping hormone-mediated drought responses. Notably, microbial influences on plant proteomes extend into deeper regulatory processes linked to chromatin organization and epigenetic control. In wheat, inoculation with native bacterial strains increased the abundance of proteins associated with histone acetylation and methylation pathways (Yadav et al., 2022). However, current knowledge remains limited by the relatively small number of microbiome-integrated proteomic studies in cereals, restricting mechanistic understanding of how specific microbial taxa reshape drought-responsive protein networks.

3.3. Epigenetic reprogramming

Proteomic evidence showing microbial regulation of chromatin-associated proteins suggests that microbiome-mediated drought adaptation may extend beyond immediate physiological responses to deeper regulatory layers. Consistent with this possibility, emerging studies indicate that drought-responsive microbiomes can influence plant adaptation through epigenetic reprogramming, thereby reshaping host responses at deeper regulatory levels. Root-associated microbes modify DNA methylation patterns, histone dynamics, and chromatin accessibility, enabling plants to adjust gene expression in ways that may persist beyond immediate stress exposure (Chen et al., 2022). Such regulation positions microbial partners not merely as transient stress alleviators, but potentially as contributors to long-term acclimation and stress memory.

One important mechanism through which microbes influence plant drought responses involves alterations in DNA methylation. Both bacterial and fungal inoculation have been shown to induce shifts in methylation profiles that coincide with improved drought tolerance (Alwutayd et al., 2023; Gagné-bourque et al., 2015; Hubbard et al., 2014; Lephatsi et al., 2022). A particularly compelling example comes from the desert root endophyte *Pseudomonas argentinensis* SA190, which enhances drought tolerance through ABA-dependent DNA methylation of aquaporin genes (Alwutayd et al., 2023). Similarly, histone modifications at stress-responsive loci such as *RD29A* and *RD29B* demonstrate direct microbial control of transcriptional activation under drought (Liu et al., 2023). These indicate that microbial partners may regulate plant stress responses not only through signal transduction but also by altering accessibility of stress-responsive loci.

Importantly, long-term plant-microbiome interactions can generate cumulative epigenetic effects with implications for stress memory. Persistent associations with beneficial endophytes have been linked to shifts in global methylation landscapes that resemble epigenetic memory formation (Forte et al., 2023). Although the stability and heritability of such microbial-induced epigenetic states remain incompletely understood, these observations raise the possibility that microbiomes may contribute to longer-term stress priming across developmental or potentially transgenerational timescales.

3.4. Transcriptomic reinforcement

At the transcriptomic level, drought-responsive microbiomes reinforce plant adaptation through extensive reprogramming of gene expression networks (Tables 1 and 2).

Consistent with metabolomic evidence showing microbiome-mediated accumulation of antioxidant and osmoprotective metabolites, transcriptomic studies indicate that microbial colonization

reinforces cellular protection through activation of stress-responsive genes. Across cereals, beneficial microbes consistently induce genes associated with antioxidant defense, osmotic adjustment, membrane stabilization, and macromolecular protection. Transcriptomic studies in rice (Bisht et al., 2025; Lee et al., 2024; Park et al., 2024) and maize (Kumar et al., 2020; SkZ et al., 2018; W. Zhang et al., 2018) demonstrate enhanced expression of antioxidant pathways. Likewise, microbial inoculation promotes expression of osmoprotective pathways, including genes associated with proline biosynthesis (*P5CS1*, *P5CS2*, and *P5CR*) and trehalose metabolism (*TPS1*), as reported in wheat inoculated with *Enterobacter bugandensis* WRS7 (Arora et al., 2023). Microbial partners can also enhance expression of genes encoding protective macromolecule stabilizers, such as *DHNS*, *LEAs*, and *HSPs* (Devarajan et al., 2021; George et al., 2024; Quazi et al., 2024; Saakre et al., 2017). These proteins mitigate the effects of cellular desiccation by preventing protein aggregation, stabilizing membranes, and acting as molecular shields.

Beyond cellular protection, microbiome-induced transcriptomic reprogramming also enhances the plant's ability to access and manage water resources under drought. Beneficial microbes improve root architectural plasticity through regulation of genes associated with cell wall loosening and root expansion. For example, inoculation with *Streptomyces pactum* Act12 and *Bacillus* consortia upregulates expansin genes (*EXP1*, *EXP2*, *EXP3*, and *EXP6*), facilitating root elongation and enabling plants to explore deeper soil layers for water acquisition (H. Li et al., 2020; Omar et al., 2021).

In parallel, microbial colonization dynamically modulates AQP gene expression to optimize water transport and maintain hydraulic balance. Interestingly, these responses appear context-dependent. In maize, AMF inoculation downregulates certain AQPs (*PIP2.4* and *TIP1.1*), potentially reducing water loss to dry soil and preserving hydraulic integrity (Quiroga et al., 2017). In contrast, microbial inoculation in sorghum and wheat upregulates alternative AQP families (*TIP2.1*, *NIP1.2*, *NIP2.2*, *TaNIP1.10*, *TaNIP3.3*, and *TaNIP3.4*), likely enhancing controlled water uptake and tissue-level redistribution (Asadollahi et al., 2023; Govindasamy et al., 2020; Symanczik et al., 2020). This apparent dichotomy highlights that microbiome-mediated hydraulic regulation is highly species- and context-dependent, reflecting fine-tuned adjustments aimed at maintaining physiological homeostasis under drought.

In addition to protective and hydraulic functions, microbiome-associated drought tolerance is frequently accompanied by induction of upstream regulatory modules that coordinate broader stress responses. Transcriptomic datasets consistently report increased abundance of transcripts encoding protein kinases, TFs, and hormonal regulators involved in stress signaling (Tables 1 and 2). Such regulatory activation suggests that beneficial microbes may prime host signaling networks, enabling plants to mount faster or more coordinated responses to drought stress. The roles of protein kinases, TFs, phytohormones, SSPs, miRNAs, and lncRNAs in microbiome-mediated drought adaptation are discussed in the following sections.

4. Microbiome-mediated modulation of plant signaling networks

4.1. Microbial modulation of plant protein kinases

Protein kinases sit at the center of plant drought signaling, functioning as molecular switches that rapidly translate environmental perturbations into coordinated physiological and transcriptional responses. Rather than acting as isolated signaling components, kinase cascades form highly interconnected networks that integrate ABA signaling, calcium dynamics, ROS regulation, and downstream stress-responsive gene activation (Mukarram et al., 2021). Within the cereal holobiont, increasing evidence suggests that root-associated microbes target these signaling hubs to fine-tune drought adaptation, thereby extending the plant's intrinsic signaling capacity under drought.

A major route through which microbes influence drought signaling

involves modulation of MAPK-associated pathways that regulate stress perception and signal amplification. For example, inoculation with *Chaetomium* sp. strain DR413 enhanced the expression of *MAPK3*, *MAPK12.1*, and *MAPK16* in wheat seedlings under water deficit (Pan et al., 2024). Likewise, colonization by *Mortierella alpina* activated several MAPK-related genes, including *MAPK3*, *MAPKKK14*, and *MAPKKK17*, alongside signaling regulators such as *CIPK9* and *PP2C30*, contributing to enhanced drought tolerance in wheat (Yue et al., 2024). Similar responses have been reported in AMF-associated cereals, where activation of MAPK pathways appears to strengthen stress-responsive signaling under drought (Huang et al., 2020; Shu et al., 2020; Yue et al., 2024).

Microbial modulation of kinase signaling becomes particularly evident in pathways linked to calcium signaling and ABA integration. Cytosolic Ca^{2+} transients represent one of the earliest responses to drought, and kinases such as CDPKs, CIPKs, and SnRK2s function as key decoders of these signals. AMF-induced activation of CDPK and CIPK pathways, therefore, points to an intimate connection between symbiotic signaling and drought-responsive calcium dynamics (Huang et al., 2020; Shu et al., 2020; Yue et al., 2024). Beneficial bacteria further reinforce this signaling layer. In rice, inoculation with *Bacillus amyloliquifaciens* and *Brevibacillus laterosporus* altered expression of *CDPK13* (Kakar et al., 2016), whereas *Pseudomonas putida* FBKV2 promoted expression of serine/threonine protein kinases (*STPKs*) associated with ABA-responsive drought pathways in maize (SkZ et al., 2018). Enhanced expression of *SnRK2* genes has also been repeatedly observed in cereal-microbe associations under drought (H. Li et al., 2020; Pan et al., 2024; W. Zhang et al., 2018). This further supports the view that microbial partners amplify ABA-dependent drought signaling through kinase-mediated regulation.

Interestingly, several kinase pathways targeted during drought are also central to plant-microbe interactions themselves. Receptor-like kinases (RLKs), MAPKs, and calcium signaling modules contribute not only to drought perception but also to arbuscular mycorrhizal signaling, arbuscule development, and symbiotic functioning through interactions with downstream transcriptional regulators, including MYB transcription factors (Das et al., 2022; Guo et al., 2022; Leng et al., 2023; Shi et al., 2022). This overlap suggests that drought signaling and symbiotic communication are not independent processes but partially integrated regulatory systems. From a holobiont perspective, root-associated microbes may therefore exploit pre-existing signaling architectures to reshape host drought responses while simultaneously maintaining beneficial associations.

4.2. Microbial modulation of stress-responsive transcription factors (TFs)

TFs function as central regulatory nodes in plant drought adaptation, coordinating large suites of downstream genes involved in osmotic adjustment, antioxidant defense, hormonal signaling, and developmental plasticity. Root-associated microbes can reshape these transcriptional networks by selectively modulating drought-responsive TF families, thereby altering how cereals perceive and respond to drought stress (Tables 1 and 2). They have been shown to induce diverse TF families, including *AP2/ERF*, *bZIP*, *WRKY*, *NAC*, *MYB*, and *bHLH* regulators, alongside stress-responsive factors such as *DREB2*, *AREB1*, *AREB2*, *bZIP1*, *ZIP23*, *WRKY47*, *NAC066*, *bHLH148*, and *JAMYB* (Bisht et al., 2025; Lee et al., 2024; Manjunatha et al., 2022; Omar et al., 2021; Park et al., 2024; Saakre et al., 2017). These transcriptional shifts are closely associated with enhanced expression of genes involved in cellular protection, ROS buffering, water balance, and metabolic adjustment under drought.

Several TF families appear to occupy particularly influential positions in microbiome-mediated drought responses. MYB and NAC TFs regulate developmental and protective processes linked to cell wall reinforcement, antioxidant metabolism, and water conservation, thereby contributing to plant resilience under dehydration stress (Mao

et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2019). Members of the AP2/ERF family, especially DREB and CBF regulators, serve as major activators of drought-responsive gene networks (Mei et al., 2022), while bZIP TFs integrate hormonal and oxidative stress signaling by coordinating ABA-responsive pathways and ROS scavenging systems (Lee and Song, 2023; Pan et al., 2022). Through modulation of these TF families, microbial partners may influence not only downstream stress-defense genes but also the broader regulatory architecture governing growth-stress tradeoffs in cereals.

Microbial effects on transcriptional regulation are not limited to bacterial interactions. AMFs and endophytic fungi similarly reshape drought-responsive transcriptional programs, influencing expression of *MYB*, *NAC*, *AP2/ERF*, *bZIP*, and other TF families (George et al., 2024; Pan et al., 2024; Quazi et al., 2024; Yue et al., 2024; W. Zhang et al., 2018). For example, AMF inoculation has been linked to increased expression of *DREB2* and *CBF* genes (from *AP2/ERF* family), which are critical for enhancing drought tolerance by triggering the production of protective proteins like dehydrins and osmoprotectants (George et al., 2024). Such responses point to a convergence between symbiotic signaling and stress-responsive transcriptional regulation, in which microbial partners help recalibrate host gene networks under environmental stress.

However, microbial modulation of TFs is unlikely to follow a universal blueprint. Different microbial taxa, host genotypes, and drought scenarios may trigger distinct transcriptional outcomes (Naylor et al., 2017; Yue et al., 2024), raising important questions about the extent to which conserved regulatory signatures exist across cereals. Clarifying these context-dependent interactions will be essential for translating microbiome-mediated transcriptional plasticity into drought-resilient crop improvement strategies.

4.3. Microbial modulation of ROS homeostasis

ROS occupy a paradoxical position in plant drought responses. While excessive ROS accumulation can damage proteins, lipids, nucleic acids, and cellular membranes, controlled ROS production also functions as a central signaling mechanism that coordinates stress perception, defense activation, and developmental adjustment under drought. Plant survival, therefore, depends not on the complete elimination of ROS, but on maintaining a tightly regulated oxidative balance through antioxidant systems, including enzymatic components such as SOD, CAT, APX, and GPX, alongside non-enzymatic antioxidants, including ascorbate, carotenoids, flavonoids, glutathione, and α -tocopherol.

Root-associated microbes play a major role in maintaining this oxidative balance under drought. Both bacterial symbionts and AMFs reduce drought-induced oxidative damage by preventing excessive ROS accumulation in plant tissues (Park et al., 2024; Singh et al., 2023). This protective effect is achieved through multiple, interconnected mechanisms, including stimulation of antioxidant enzyme activities (Shan et al., 2025; Singh et al., 2023), induction of host antioxidant gene expression (Lee et al., 2024; Park et al., 2024), enhanced accumulation of antioxidant proteins (Nivedita et al., 2024; Quazi et al., 2024; Tanveer et al., 2024), and shifts in plant metabolite profiles that favor antioxidant production (El-Shazoly et al., 2025; Hagaggi and Abdul-Rauf, 2022; Jerbi et al., 2022). Through these complementary processes, microbial partners help buffer oxidative stress while preserving ROS-mediated signaling required for adaptive responses.

Yet, ROS regulation within the plant-microbiome system extends beyond stress mitigation. Emerging evidence suggests that plants actively use ROS as ecological signals to shape rhizosphere microbial communities. By integrating mutant analyses with multi-omics approaches, Sun et al. (2024) demonstrated that localized H_2O_2 release from Arabidopsis roots creates an oxidative niche that selectively enriches ROS-tolerant and potentially beneficial microorganisms, including nitrogen-fixing *Cyanobacteria*. These findings suggest that ROS are not solely by-products of stress but may function as ecological filters

that influence microbiome assembly under drought. Such bidirectional regulation highlights a dynamic feedback loop in which microbes modulate host oxidative status, while plants simultaneously use ROS signals to recruit microbial partners adapted to stressful environments.

The dynamic nature of microbiome-mediated ROS regulation becomes particularly evident during fungal colonization. AMFs contribute to localized ROS control through specialized structures such as arbuscules and extraradical hyphae, processes that are critical for maintaining symbiosis and facilitating stress adaptation (Esparza-Reynoso et al., 2023; Sun et al., 2024; Wu et al., 2023). An especially illustrative example comes from the endophytic fungus *Trichoderma atroviride*, which exhibits a temporally coordinated strategy of ROS modulation (Esparza-Reynoso et al., 2023). During early root colonization, microbial volatile compounds and rhizosphere acidification transiently

elevate ROS accumulation in root tips, creating signaling conditions favorable for fungal establishment. As colonization progresses, however, the fungus suppresses host NADPH oxidases, including *RBOHA*, *RBOHD*, and *RBOHE*, thereby limiting excessive ROS accumulation and promoting beneficial changes in root architecture. Since respiratory burst oxidase homologs (RBOHs) are key mediators of ROS production and drought adaptation (Chen et al., 2024; H. Gao et al., 2022), their microbial regulation illustrates how beneficial microbes fine-tune oxidative signaling rather than simply suppressing oxidative stress.

4.4. Microbial modulation of phytohormone biosynthesis and signaling

Root-associated microorganisms reshape drought adaptation by modulating interconnected phytohormonal networks rather than

Fig. 2. Microbial-mediated drought stress signaling pathways in cereal crops. The schematic integrates key rhizosphere microbiome interactions that modulate plant drought responses through (1) Signal initiation: Microbial-mediated phytohormones such as ABA, AUX, GA, ETH, SA, JA, and CK initiate stress perception and response in plant roots. (2) Signal transduction: Microbial enhancement of ROS/Ca²⁺ signaling and MAPK cascades contributes to transducing stress signals. (3) Transcriptional reprogramming: Rhizosphere microbes induce activation of drought-responsive TFs (NACs, DREBs, WRKY families, MYB/MYCs, AREBs, etc.), which upregulate drought-responsive genes (RD29B, RAB16, LEAs, DHNs, antioxidants, osmolytes, HSPs), and promote physiological adaptations in plants. Question marks indicate pathways with extremely limited information (BR and SL pathways, as well as small peptides), while genes identified in cereal crops are presented by solid circular symbols. Black arrows (→): Activation or positive regulation; Red blunt-ended lines (—): Inhibition or suppression; Dotted lines (····>): Indirect regulation or interaction; Color-coded components: Phytohormone-specific pathways (AUX (Dark navy blue), JA (Dark navy blue), SA (Turquoise), ETH (Light pink), and GA (Brown), Protein Kinases (Persian blue), and TFs (Emerald). Together, this framework highlights drought adaptation as an emergent property of coordinated interkingdom signaling rather than isolated hormonal responses.

individual hormone pathways. An overview of these microbial-hormonal interactions is presented in Fig. 2, which integrates phytohormone regulation, intracellular signaling cascades, and transcriptional reprogramming into a systems-level framework of cereal drought responses. These effects largely emerge through hormonal crosstalk, particularly ABA-centered interactions.

ABA: Central coordination of drought adaptation and microbiome assembly. Among drought-responsive phytohormones, ABA occupies a central regulatory role in coordinating plant adaptation to water deficit. It regulates stomatal closure to limit water loss, enhances antioxidant defenses, reshapes root architecture to improve water acquisition, and promotes the accumulation of protective metabolites that mitigate dehydration stress (Jogawat et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2024). Beyond these endogenous functions, increasing evidence suggests that ABA also acts as an ecological signal linking plant drought physiology with microbiome assembly.

Drought consistently elevates ABA concentrations in cereal root exudates (Caddell et al., 2023; G. Li et al., 2023). This shift not only reflects activation of plant stress signaling but also influences rhizosphere composition, favoring drought-associated taxa, particularly *Actinobacteria* (Ma et al., 2022). Such findings position ABA as a bidirectional signal that simultaneously coordinates host stress responses and selects microbial partners capable of enhancing drought resilience.

Microbial communities, in turn, actively reshape ABA homeostasis and signaling in host plants. Several root-associated microorganisms enriched under drought, including *Azospirillum sp.* (Curá et al., 2017), *Bacillus subtilis* (Barnawal et al., 2017; Ilyas et al., 2020), *Klebsiella aerogenes* (Shaffique et al., 2023), and AMFs (Charesri et al., 2020; H. Li et al., 2020), have been shown to synthesize ABA or stimulate ABA-related pathways in plants. In pearl millet, inoculation with *Shewanella putrefaciens* MCL-1 and *Cronobacter dublinensis* MKS-1 increased the expression of *NCED*, a major ABA biosynthetic gene, leading to enhanced drought tolerance (Manjunatha et al., 2022).

In parallel, the desert-derived bacterium *Pseudomonas argentinensis* SA190 enhanced drought tolerance in *Arabidopsis* through ABA-dependent remodeling of root architecture and transcriptional reprogramming (Alwutayd et al., 2023). This response involved activation of ABA receptors (*PYL1*, *PYL3*), ABA-responsive kinases (*SnRK2.3*), and phosphatases (*HAI1*, *HAI2*). Fungal partners similarly participate in microbial regulation of ABA signaling. In wheat, colonization by the drought-enriched fungus *Chaetomium sp.* DR413 enhanced root growth and activated ABA-associated regulatory networks under drought (Pan et al., 2024). This interaction increased expression of genes involved in ABA perception and signaling, including *PP2C-a7*, *PP2C-a10*, *PP2C-a30*, *SnRK2.9*, several *MAPKs*, and downstream TFs such as *bZIP15*, *NAC2*, and *SIM*. These coordinated transcriptional changes suggest that microbial modulation of ABA signaling extends beyond simple hormone accumulation and instead involves broad rewiring of drought-responsive regulatory circuits.

Collectively, these findings position ABA as a central interkingdom signaling hub through which plants and root-associated microbiomes coordinate drought adaptation. Rather than acting solely as a plant-derived stress hormone, ABA appears to mediate reciprocal interactions in which host drought responses influence microbiome assembly, while microbial partners simultaneously reinforce plant resilience by reshaping ABA biosynthesis and signaling.

ETH: Balancing drought trade-offs and microbiome assembly. ETH plays a complex and highly context-dependent role in plant drought responses. Synthesized from methionine through the sequential action of ACC synthase (ACS) and ACC oxidase (ACO), ETH regulates diverse physiological processes associated with stress adaptation, including stomatal behavior, root growth, senescence, and stress-responsive transcriptional networks. In cereals, key components of ETH biosynthesis and signaling, including *ETR/CTR*, *EIN2*, and members of the *AP2/ERF* TF family, have been implicated in drought adaptation (Li et al., 2018). However, the role of ETH during water limitation is not

uniformly beneficial. Instead, drought responses emerge from a finely tuned hormonal balance in which ETH interacts extensively with ABA signaling. Under moderate stress, ETH can synergize with ABA to support adaptive responses, whereas prolonged or severe drought often shifts ETH signaling toward growth inhibition and accelerated senescence (Müller, 2021).

ETH also contributes to microbiome assembly, highlighting its broader role as an interkingdom signaling molecule. ETH signaling has been associated with the selective recruitment and maintenance of drought-associated microbial taxa, particularly members of the *Actinobacteria*, which frequently accumulate in drought-stressed cereal rhizospheres (Fu et al., 2021). Because many of these taxa confer benefits related to osmoprotection, nutrient acquisition, and hormonal modulation, ETH may function as a hormonal filter that shapes microbial recruitment under drought. This dual role positions ETH not only as a regulator of plant stress physiology but also as an important determinant of rhizosphere community composition.

Microbial partners, in turn, actively modulate ETH biosynthesis and signaling, often by reducing excessive ETH accumulation that can become detrimental under drought. A major mechanism involves microbial production of ACC deaminase (AcdS), an enzyme that degrades ACC, the immediate precursor of ETH (Poudel et al., 2021). By lowering ACC availability, beneficial microbes can attenuate ETH production and alleviate drought-associated growth inhibition. Root-associated bacteria such as *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* and *Pseudomonas putida* reduce the expression of ETH biosynthesis and signaling genes in drought-stressed cereals, including *ACO35*, *ACS47*, *ERF11*, and *ERF1B*, thereby improving stress tolerance in maize and millet (Murali et al., 2021; SkZ et al., 2018).

The functional importance of microbial ETH modulation is supported by mutant evidence. In rice, *Enterobacter aerogenes* improved root growth and rhizosheath formation under moderate drought, effects that were tightly linked to its ACC deaminase activity (Zhang et al., 2020). Notably, these benefits disappeared in an *AcdS*⁻ mutant deficient in ACC degradation, providing strong functional evidence for microbial regulation of ETH as a mechanism of drought alleviation.

However, microbial manipulation of ETH signaling does not always produce uniform outcomes. In *Arabidopsis*, for example, plants inoculated with an isogenic *AcdS*⁻ mutant of *Pseudomonas putida* UW4 unexpectedly showed improved survival during prolonged drought relative to plants colonized by the wild type strain (Hecht et al., 2025). In this case, sustained ETH signaling promoted stronger stomatal closure and more conservative water use. These contrasting observations suggest that the adaptive value of microbial ETH modulation may depend on drought severity, host genotype, and interactions with other hormonal pathways, particularly ABA signaling. Rather than simply suppressing ETH, beneficial microbes may therefore fine-tune ETH dynamics to optimize the trade-off between water conservation, growth, and survival.

AUX/IAA: Developmental plasticity and root adaptation. Among developmental phytohormones, AUX/IAA plays a central role in enabling plants to adjust root architecture in response to drought. Because water availability is spatially heterogeneous in drying soils, drought adaptation depends not only on stress perception but also on developmental plasticity that allows roots to optimize water uptake. AUX signaling regulates key processes underlying this plasticity, including lateral root formation, root hair development, and directional root growth (Uga et al., 2013). Importantly, AUX signaling operates in close coordination with ABA, integrating developmental adjustment with stress signaling to maintain adaptive root growth while minimizing energetic costs under drought (Qiao et al., 2023; K. Xu et al., 2023).

Beyond root development, AUX also contributes to plant-microbiome interactions, particularly during the establishment of beneficial symbioses. Evidence from AMF systems highlights this role clearly. In rice, disruption of auxin signaling or transport markedly impaired AMF colonization (Wang et al., 2024). Mutants defective in the

exocyst component EXO70L2 (*sr1* mutant) exhibited a reduced expression of auxin-associated genes, including *IAA*, *PIN*, *YUCCA*, *FIB*, and *AAO*, resulting in defective lateral root development, impaired arbuscule formation, and reduced AMF colonization. These findings suggest that AUX signaling functions not only in root development but also as an important regulator of microbial accommodation within the rhizosphere.

Microbial partners reciprocally influence host AUX pathways to enhance drought adaptation. Diverse root-associated microbes, including *Shewanella putrefaciens*, *Cronobacter dublinensis*, *Pseudomonas putida*, and *Piriformospora indica*, regulate genes associated with auxin biosynthesis and signaling, including *YUC* family genes, *GH3.8*, *SAUR56*, and *AUX/IAA* regulators (Manjunatha et al., 2022; SkZ et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2022; W. Zhang et al., 2018). Through these interactions, microbial partners reshape root architecture and strengthen developmental responses that improve water uptake under drought.

The functional significance of microbial AUX modulation becomes particularly evident in studies using host mutants impaired in auxin biology. In *Arabidopsis*, inoculation with *Achromobacter* sp. 5B1 restored root growth in mutants defective in auxin transport (*aux1*, *eir1*), perception (*tir1* *afb2* *afb3*), and signaling (*axr1*, *arf7* *arf19*) (Jimenez-Vazquez et al., 2020). Mechanistically, the bacterium promoted auxin redistribution through AUX1/EIR1-dependent transport and enhanced signaling through the TIR1/AFB-ARF regulatory module, partially compensating for defects in host AUX pathways. These findings provide compelling evidence that beneficial microbes do not merely stimulate plant growth but actively reinforce core developmental signaling networks during drought. Similarly, in barley, only IAA-producing strains of *Chryseobacterium culicis* and *Paenibacillus polymyxa* promoted root hair elongation, vegetative growth, and grain yield under drought, whereas IAA-deficient mutants (*trpC*, *ipdC*) failed to confer these benefits (F. Xu et al., 2023). Together, these findings directly support a functional role for microbial auxin in host drought adaptation.

Microbial influences on AUX signaling are not limited to canonical IAA pathways. Recently identified pteridic acids produced by *Streptomyces* species exhibit auxin-like activity and promote root growth across multiple plant systems, including *Arabidopsis*, barley, and mung bean (Yang et al., 2023). These compounds triggered broader transcriptional responses involving auxin transport (*PIN6*, *FRO6*), signaling regulators (*IAA6/29*, *SAURs*), and drought-associated TFs, including *MYB*, *WRKY*, *bHLH*, *bZIP*, and *AP2/ERF*. Such findings raise the possibility that microbial metabolites may function as hormone mimics, simultaneously activating developmental and stress-responsive programs that extend beyond classical auxin signaling.

Within the cereal holobiont, AUX therefore emerges as more than a developmental hormone. By coordinating root plasticity, microbial accommodation, and drought-responsive growth adjustments, auxin signaling provides an important interface through which microbial partners help plants optimize resource acquisition under water-limited conditions.

CKs: Growth buffering and microbial partnerships. CKs contribute to drought resilience by buffering the physiological costs of stress while preserving growth potential. Unlike ABA-centered pathways that prioritize water conservation and growth restriction, CK signaling often acts to preserve physiological activity under stress, preventing excessive metabolic decline during prolonged water limitation. In cereals, CKs contribute to drought resilience by enhancing antioxidant capacity, maintaining photosynthetic performance, regulating nutrient allocation, and promoting osmotic adjustment (Huang et al., 2018; Vojta et al., 2016). Importantly, CK function is tightly integrated with ABA signaling, and the balance between these pathways appears to fine-tune drought adaptation by coordinating trade-offs between growth maintenance and stress survival (Huang et al., 2018).

Beyond plant physiology, CKs contribute to microbiome assembly and symbiotic interactions, reinforcing their role within the cereal

holobiont. Evidence suggests that CK signaling influences recruitment of beneficial microbial taxa, particularly members of the *Firmicutes*, while also facilitating AMF colonization in plant roots (Cosme et al., 2016; Gupta et al., 2021). These observations indicate that CKs function not only as endogenous regulators of stress adaptation but also as ecological mediators shaping microbial partnerships under drought.

Microbial communities reciprocally influence CK homeostasis through both direct hormone production and regulation of host signaling pathways. Several root-associated bacteria, including *Methylobacterium*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*, and *Azospirillum brasilense*, are capable of synthesizing CKs (Mekureyaw et al., 2022; Palberg et al., 2022; Timofeeva et al., 2024). Such microbial CK production can substantially alter plant physiology under water limitation. In maize, colonization by *Piriformospora indica* regulated key CK-responsive regulators, including *ARR2* and *ARR9*, promoting adaptive modifications in root architecture and improving water uptake during drought (W. Zhang et al., 2018).

Functional evidence for microbial CK-mediated drought protection has emerged from studies using defined inoculants and hormone-deficient mutants. In wheat, inoculation with the zeatin-producing strain *Azospirillum brasilense* RA-17 enhanced plant growth, yield, antioxidant activity, osmolyte accumulation, and endogenous hormone balance under drought stress (Zaheer and Ali, 2022). Similarly, *Bacillus subtilis* IB-22 was shown to modify wheat root metabolism through CK-associated mechanisms (Kudoyarova et al., 2014). Mechanistic support comes from work with *Pseudomonas fluorescens* G20-18, a well-characterized CK-producing bacterium. In tomato, colonization by the wild-type strain induced expression of drought-responsive genes involved in osmotic adjustment, antioxidant defenses, and water transport, whereas CK-deficient mutants lacking *cnt1* and *cnt2* failed to trigger these protective responses (Mekureyaw et al., 2022). Plants inoculated with the mutant strains displayed reduced water potential, lower stomatal conductance, impaired growth, and elevated oxidative stress relative to those colonized by the CK-producing wild type.

Within the drought-stressed cereal holobiont, CK signaling therefore appears to function as a buffering mechanism that tempers the physiological costs of stress while preserving growth potential. Through microbial modulation of CK biosynthesis and signaling, beneficial microorganisms may help plants maintain metabolic activity and developmental flexibility under drought, complementing the survival-oriented functions of ABA-centered stress networks.

GAs: Growth reallocation and microbial symbiosis. GAs are central regulators of plant growth, controlling processes such as stem elongation, cell expansion, and reproductive development. Under drought, however, maintaining unrestricted growth becomes metabolically costly and can accelerate water loss. Plants therefore frequently suppress GA biosynthesis and signaling as part of an adaptive transition from growth-oriented metabolism toward stress survival. This shift is typically accompanied by reduced expression of GA biosynthetic genes, including *GA20ox1*, and the accumulation of DELLA proteins, which function as master negative regulators of GA signaling (Liao et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2024). Through repression of growth-promoting programs, DELLA accumulation reduces transpiration demand, limits energy expenditure, and reallocates resources toward stress protection, often in coordination with ABA signaling (Liao et al., 2023).

GA signaling also participates in shaping beneficial plant-microbe interactions, particularly AMF symbiosis. Accumulating evidence suggests that drought adaptation and microbial colonization are mechanistically linked through DELLA-dependent signaling. Reduced GA activity favors AMF establishment by promoting arbuscule development and stabilizing symbiotic interactions (Aviles-Cardenas et al., 2024; Seemann et al., 2021). Mechanistically, DELLA proteins interact with key symbiosis regulators such as CYCLOPS and GRAS-domain TFs, directly or indirectly influencing expression of mycorrhiza-associated genes required for fungal colonization and nutrient exchange (Aviles-Cardenas et al., 2024; Seemann et al., 2021). These observations

suggest that drought-induced suppression of GA signaling may simultaneously strengthen microbial partnerships, reinforcing adaptive capacity under water limitation.

Microbial partners, in turn, actively influence GA homeostasis through both direct and indirect mechanisms. Several beneficial microorganisms have been shown to produce bioactive GAs or stimulate host GA biosynthesis under drought conditions (Carlson et al., 2020; Manjunatha et al., 2022; Yasmin et al., 2017). Root-associated microbes isolated from sorghum, including *Acinetobacter pittii*, *Bacillus licheniformis*, *Bacillus spp.*, *Pseudacidovorax intermedius*, and *Acinetobacter baumannii*, produce substantial quantities of GAs (Umapathi et al., 2022), highlighting the widespread capacity of rhizosphere microorganisms to modulate growth-associated hormonal pools.

The adaptive value of microbial GA modulation becomes particularly apparent in multispecies interactions. In maize, co-inoculation with the drought-resistant strains *Bacillus cereus* DS4 and *Bacillus albus* DS9 enhanced seed germination and seedling vigor more effectively than either strain alone under drought stress (Ashry et al., 2022). These complementary effects likely reflect functional cooperation between microbial hormones: while *B. cereus* DS4 produces IAA to stimulate root development and water acquisition, *B. albus* DS9 synthesizes GAs that support plant growth and stress recovery. Such synergistic interactions emphasize that microbiome-mediated drought adaptation may emerge not from single microbial traits, but from coordinated hormonal activities distributed across microbial consortia.

Unlike ABA-centered stress pathways, microbial regulation of GA signaling appears to operate primarily through optimization of the growth-survival balance. Within the cereal holobiont, GA dynamics may therefore function as a flexible regulatory layer through which microbial partners help plants calibrate developmental investment according to drought severity, allowing growth to continue without compromising stress resilience.

BRs: Growth maintenance and microbial accommodation. BRs contribute to drought tolerance by coordinating physiological adjustments that preserve plant growth and cellular function under drought. In cereals, BR signaling has been associated with enhanced photosynthetic efficiency, improved leaf water retention, stronger antioxidant defenses, increased osmolyte accumulation, and lignification processes that support tissue integrity during dehydration (Avalbaev et al., 2024; Faheem et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2019). Central regulators of the BR pathway, including *BIN2*, *BZR1*, and *BAK1*, orchestrate these adaptive responses while maintaining extensive crosstalk with ABA signaling components such as *ABI1*, *ABI2*, *ABI5*, and *SnRK2*, enabling plants to balance growth maintenance with drought defense (Gao et al., 2024).

BR signaling also enhanced fungal entry and arbuscule formation, in part through regulation of genes involved in cell-wall remodeling and symbiotic signaling (*SIBR1*, *SLUPD3*) together with downstream processes associated with cytoskeleton organization and nutrient transport (Y. Ren et al., 2024). These BR-mediated changes facilitate fungal accommodation and efficient nutrient exchange, indicating that hormonal pathways involved in drought adaptation may simultaneously regulate microbial recruitment. From a holobiont perspective, BR signaling may therefore function as an integrative hub that coordinates stress resilience with symbiotic establishment.

Compared with other phytohormones, evidence for direct microbial modulation of BR pathways remains limited. Nevertheless, several studies provide indirect indications that beneficial microbes, including *Bacillus spp.*, *Pseudomonas spp.*, and the AMF *Funneliformis mosseae*, may influence BR homeostasis under drought (Bernardo et al., 2019; Carlson et al., 2020; Haimlich et al., 2024). Particularly compelling evidence comes from the discovery of a microbial DET2 homologue, involved in BR biosynthesis, in drought-alleviating *Actinobacteria*. Expression of this microbial gene in the *Arabidopsis det2* mutant restored normal plant growth, demonstrating that microbial functions can compensate for disrupted host hormonal deficiencies (Haimlich et al., 2024).

Although current evidence remains fragmentary, BR signaling

represents an emerging frontier in cereal-microbiome research. Rather than acting solely as a plant growth regulator, BR may participate in synchronizing drought adaptation with microbial assembly, helping roots maintain productive symbioses under drought. Clarifying whether beneficial microbes directly regulate BR biosynthesis, signaling sensitivity, or receptor activity in cereals will be essential for understanding how microbial partners contribute to drought resilience through hormonal integration.

JA: Drought signaling and stress priming. Although JA is traditionally associated with defense against herbivores and pathogens, growing evidence demonstrates that it also contributes substantially to drought resilience by regulating stomatal conductance, antioxidant defenses, osmotic adjustment, and root system architecture (Awan et al., 2021; Muzaffar et al., 2024). Importantly, JA rarely acts independently. Instead, it is tightly interconnected with ABA signaling, forming an integrated regulatory network that coordinates physiological and transcriptional responses under water deficit (Fu et al., 2017).

In addition to regulating host physiology, JA participates in structuring beneficial plant-microbe associations. Emerging evidence suggests that JA signaling contributes to the selective recruitment of advantageous root-associated microorganisms. In rice, JA-dependent signaling pathways regulate the assembly of beneficial endophytic communities (Liu et al., 2018). Similarly, exogenous JA application in wheat reshaped root microbial communities, altering the relative abundance of specific Actinobacterial taxa and AMFs (Liu et al., 2017). These observations suggest that JA signaling extends beyond internal plant defense and acts as a determinant of rhizosphere organization, linking drought-responsive physiology with microbiome recruitment.

Microbial communities reciprocally influence JA biosynthesis and signaling, thereby reinforcing plant drought adaptation. Several beneficial microorganisms have been shown to activate JA-mediated responses in crops such as wheat and maize, as well as in model systems including *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Ahmad et al., 2019; Bernardo et al., 2017; Gomez et al., 2023). Inoculation with *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* IRAT FA3 reduced osmotic stress in its host, an effect associated with elevated JA accumulation and rapid modulation of stress-related gene expression (Gomez et al., 2023). Functional evidence from *myc2* and *jar1* mutants further demonstrated that intact JA signaling is essential for microbial enhancement of drought tolerance, confirming that microbial benefits can depend on activation of core host JA pathways.

Microbial regulation of JA signaling also directly influences drought-responsive physiology. Colonization by *Aeromonas sp.* H1 stimulated accumulation of H₂O₂ in guard cells during dehydration, promoting stomatal closure and reducing water loss through transpiration (He et al., 2022). This response coincided with increased expression of JA biosynthesis and signaling genes, including *AOC1*, *AOS*, and *JAZ7*, indicating that microbial activation of JA signaling coordinates both transcriptional and physiological drought defenses. Together, these findings position JA as more than a canonical defense hormone. Within the drought-stressed cereal holobiont, JA functions as a regulatory bridge linking microbial colonization and plant physiology.

SA: Fine-tuning drought resilience through microbial interactions: Although SA is classically recognized for its role in plant immunity, accumulating evidence indicates that it also contributes substantially to drought adaptation. Under drought, SA signaling regulates a broad range of physiological and molecular processes, including stomatal behavior, nutrient uptake, chlorophyll maintenance, photosynthetic efficiency, membrane stability, antioxidant defenses, and transcriptional reprogramming (Khalvandi et al., 2021; Proadhan et al., 2018; Shan et al., 2024). Through these coordinated functions, SA helps plants maintain cellular homeostasis while limiting drought-induced physiological damage.

SA also participates in the organization of beneficial root-associated microbial communities. As a central regulator of systemic acquired resistance, SA has traditionally been viewed through the lens of plant defense. However, emerging evidence suggests that SA-dependent

signaling pathways are also engaged during beneficial microbial interactions, including bacterial colonization and AMF symbiosis (Lebeis et al., 2015; Medina et al., 2003). In *Arabidopsis thaliana*, mutants impaired in SA signaling (*jar1ein2npr1* and *ein2npr1*) exhibited substantial shifts in rhizosphere microbiome composition, characterized by reduced abundance of *Actinobacteria* and *Firmicutes* alongside enrichment of *Proteobacteria* (Lebeis et al., 2015). These observations suggest that SA signaling contributes to microbial filtering, helping shape rhizosphere communities under stressful environments.

SA further mediates interkingdom interactions through functions that extend beyond host signaling. In the rhizosphere, SA serves as a precursor for siderophore biosynthesis, supporting microbial iron acquisition under nutrient-limited conditions (Timofeeva et al., 2024). This interaction may generate reciprocal benefits: microbial siderophores improve nutrient availability and microbial competitiveness, while SA-associated signaling simultaneously primes plant stress responses. Such reciprocal exchange highlights the increasingly recognized role of SA as a mediator of cooperation within the drought-stressed holobiont.

Root-associated microorganisms, in turn, actively modulate SA-associated pathways to optimize host performance during drought. Several beneficial taxa, including species of *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, and *Azospirillum*, have been associated with enhanced drought tolerance through activation or modulation of SA-responsive pathways (Carlson et al., 2020; Cho et al., 2008; Jochum et al., 2019). However, microbial influences on SA signaling are not universally stimulatory. In drought-stressed wheat, inoculation with *Bacillus sp.* and *Paenibacillus beijingensis* reduced expression of *PRI*, a canonical marker of SA signaling (Li et al., 2019). This suppression suggests that beneficial microbes may fine-tune SA activity to avoid excessive defense activation, thereby reducing metabolic costs and preserving growth under water limitation. Hence, rather than functioning solely as a defense hormone, SA appears to mediate a dynamic balance between stress protection, microbial recruitment, and resource allocation. By modulating SA signaling, microbial partners may help plants optimize the trade-off between defense activation and drought adaptation, reinforcing resilience without incurring unnecessary physiological costs.

SLs: Emerging interkingdom signals. SLs are increasingly recognized as important regulators of plant adaptation to drought, functioning at the intersection of developmental plasticity, stress signaling, and microbial communication. Under water-limited conditions, SLs contribute to drought resilience by preserving photosynthetic performance, strengthening antioxidant defenses, promoting osmolyte accumulation, and improving water-use efficiency (Luqman et al., 2023; Song et al., 2023). SL signaling also influences root system architecture, enhancing soil exploration and water acquisition, while facilitating stomatal regulation to reduce transpiration losses (Guo et al., 2023; Y. Zhang et al., 2018). Functional interactions between SL and ABA pathways further suggest that SL signaling contributes to the full activation of drought-adaptive responses, positioning SLs as important modulators of hormonal crosstalk during water deficit (Korek and Marzec, 2023).

Similar to other drought-associated phytohormones, SLs contribute to shaping microbial associations, particularly through their involvement in AMF establishment. During nutrient limitation and drought, roots exude SLs into the surrounding soil, where they function as potent attractants for AMFs, stimulating fungal branching, colonization, and arbuscule formation (Choi et al., 2020; Kobae et al., 2018; Yuan et al., 2023). Through this mechanism, SL signaling enhances microbial partnerships that improve nutrient acquisition, hydraulic conductivity, and stress buffering under drought. From a holobiont perspective, SLs therefore represent more than endogenous hormones; they function as ecological signals that actively shape beneficial microbiome recruitment during environmental stress.

Evidence from genetic studies further supports this role in microbiome assembly. In sorghum, disruption of *CCD8b*, a key gene in SL biosynthesis, through CRISPR/Cas9-mediated mutagenesis significantly

altered both bacterial and fungal diversity in the rhizosphere (Hao et al., 2023). These findings suggest that SL production contributes to structuring the root microbiome and may influence the establishment of drought-adaptive microbial consortia. Given the central role of AMFs in cereal drought resilience, SL-mediated microbial recruitment may represent a crucial mechanism through which plants extend their adaptive capacity beyond their own genome.

Despite this ecological importance, direct evidence for microbial feedback regulation of SL pathways remains scarce. To date, few studies have examined whether beneficial microbes actively modulate SL biosynthesis or signaling components such as *D27*, *CCD7/8*, *D14*, or *MAX2* (Upadhyay, 2026). This represents an important knowledge gap, particularly because SL signaling occupies a strategic position linking root architecture, stress physiology, and microbial symbiosis. Understanding whether microbial partners can reshape SL dynamics may reveal new opportunities to engineer cereal holobionts with enhanced drought resilience.

4.5. Microbial modulation of small signaling peptides (SSPs) and peptide hormones

SSPs represent a rapidly expanding class of plant signaling regulators that typically range from 5 to 100 amino acids and originate either from larger precursor proteins or directly from small open reading frames (G. Ren et al., 2024). Although structurally simple, SSPs serve as powerful systemic messengers, enabling plants to translate localized root water sensing into coordinated whole-plant adaptive responses during drought (Takahashi et al., 2018). Perception of SSPs occurs through RLKs, which activate downstream phosphorylation cascades and can integrate with phytohormone pathways and ROS-associated signaling hubs (Smith et al., 2020; Tian et al., 2022). This regulatory integration positions SSPs as important signaling intermediates connecting local drought perception with broader adaptive responses.

A canonical example of SSPs is the *Arabidopsis* peptide CLE25, which moves from drought-stressed roots to aerial tissues and induces ABA biosynthesis by activating *NCED3*, resulting in stomatal closure and reduced transpiration (Takahashi et al., 2018). Another well-characterized group, the CEP family, operates as long-distance root-derived signals whose perception by CEPR1/2 fine-tunes ABA transport and signaling (Zhang et al., 2021). Under drought, reduced CEPR1/2 kinase activity limits phosphorylation of ABA transporters and receptors, thereby enhancing ABA sensitivity and reinforcing drought adaptation. Members of the cysteine-rich peptide (CRP) family also contribute to drought adaptation through regulation of ABA signaling and ROS homeostasis (Cui et al., 2018; Li et al., 2017). More recently, miRNA-encoded peptides (miPEPs) have emerged as drought-responsive regulators. In rice, miPEP172b enhanced drought tolerance through modulation of miRNA-mediated hormone and ROS signaling (Lu et al., 2025).

Beyond drought signaling, increasing evidence suggests that SSPs also participate in microbiome-associated regulation, linking plant stress responses with microbial interactions (Nakagami et al., 2024; Torres Ascurra and Müller, 2025). They can fine-tune symbiotic associations by balancing plant resource allocation and microbial colonization. For instance, certain CLEs act as negative regulators, limiting AMF colonization to maintain cost-benefit homeostasis for host plants (Müller et al., 2019; Wulf et al., 2023). In contrast, some CLE peptides, such as *MtCLE16*, positively regulate symbiosis, promoting the formation and maintenance of arbuscules (Bashyal et al., 2025). *MtCLE16* promotes arbuscule development by modulating ROS and immune signaling through the pseudo-kinase receptor *MtCRN*. Remarkably, peptide-based communication in the holobiont can be bidirectional. *Rhizophagus irregularis* produces a CLE-like peptide mimic, *RiCLE1*, which promotes colonization through the host receptor *MtCRN* and enhances AMF establishment (Le Marquer et al., 2019). This indicates that microbial peptide mimics can directly modulate host signaling to favor symbiosis.

All together suggest that SSPs function not only as internal regulators of drought adaptation but also as signaling interfaces connecting plants with their associated microbiomes. Within the cereal holobiont, microbial modulation or mimicry of peptide signaling may represent an additional regulatory layer through which beneficial microbes influence drought resilience. However, mechanistic evidence remains limited, particularly in cereals, highlighting an important frontier for future microbiome research.

4.6. Microbiome-induced miRNAs

miRNAs are endogenous small RNAs (20-24 nucleotides) that silence or down-regulate gene expression at the post-transcriptional level by guiding the cleavage or translational repression of target mRNAs (Kaur et al., 2024). In cereals, drought-responsive miRNAs modulate a wide range of physiological and molecular processes, including stomatal regulation, root growth and development, amino-acid biosynthesis, antioxidant defense, flavonoid pathway, phytohormone, and protein-kinase signaling (Palakolanu et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023; Zhou et al., 2024). These enhance the plant's capacity to maintain water balance, reduce oxidative damage, and sustain growth under drought.

Increasing evidence indicates that miRNAs also participate in microbiome-associated regulation, linking post-transcriptional control with beneficial root-microbe interactions. In particular, several AMF-responsive miRNAs act on key components of nutrient signaling pathways and transcriptional regulators required for arbuscule development (Couzigou et al., 2017; Etemadi et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2018). Silencing of *AGO7*, a component of the RNA-induced silencing complex (RISC), further increased AMF colonization, whereas overexpression of *miR473* and *miRNA-PN59* reduced mycorrhization by targeting phytohormone signaling and fatty acid metabolism pathways involved in fungal accommodation (Baldwin et al., 2023). These findings suggest that miRNAs help fine-tune microbial colonization by balancing symbiotic establishment with host regulatory programs. Additionally, plant-derived miRNAs released into the rhizosphere can influence microbial gene expression and function (Middleton et al., 2024), potentially extending miRNA-mediated signaling beyond the plant itself.

Microbial colonization can also reshape host miRNA profiles, thereby reinforcing drought adaptation through post-transcriptional regulation (Aydinoglu et al., 2023; Fileccia et al., 2019). In wheat, inoculation with a mycorrhizal consortium of *Rhizophagus irregularis* and *Funneliformis mosseae* under drought repressed *miR394*, *miR167e-3p*, and *miR9666*, influencing ABA sensitivity and auxin-mediated root development (Fileccia et al., 2019). Similarly, *Piriformospora indica* colonization in rice upregulated *miR396* and *miR159*, enhancing drought tolerance through regulation of Growth-Regulating Factors (GRFs) and MYB TFs (Fard et al., 2017). In maize, *Azospirillum brasilense* modulated several drought-responsive miRNAs, including *miR159*, *miR164*, *miR169*, *miR396*, and *miR399*, which are associated with transcription factor activity and phytohormone signaling (Espindula and Passaglia, 2024). These findings demonstrate that microbial modulation of host miRNAs is a key mechanism shaping stress-responsive gene networks in plants; however, detailed investigation of these interactions in cereal systems is still emerging and is growing in research interest.

4.7. Microbiome-mediated lncRNA-miRNA regulatory networks

Long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs) are non-protein-coding transcripts (>200 nucleotides) that regulate gene expression through transcriptional, epigenetic, and post-transcriptional mechanisms (Devadhasan et al., 2025). In cereals, drought-responsive lncRNAs have emerged as key regulators of plant responses to drought stress by modulating pathways involved in hormone signaling, antioxidant defense, osmotic adjustment, and root system architecture (Cai et al., 2024; Cheng et al., 2024; Pang et al., 2019; Qin et al., 2017). An important regulatory function of lncRNAs during drought involves their interaction with

miRNAs. Acting as competing endogenous RNAs, lncRNAs can sequester specific miRNAs and thereby relieve repression of stress-responsive target genes. Such lncRNA-miRNA-mRNA regulatory networks have been reported in rice and wheat, where they fine-tune drought-responsive pathways associated with ABA signaling, stress perception, and cellular protection (Chen et al., 2021; Li et al., 2022; Qiu et al., 2025).

In addition to their well-established roles in drought tolerance, lncRNAs have increasingly been recognized as modulators of plant-microbiome interactions, extending their regulatory roles into the cereal holobiont (Han et al., 2019; L. Li et al., 2023; Traubenik et al., 2020). Colonization by AMFs substantially reprograms host lncRNA expression. In maize, AMF inoculation altered lncRNAs associated with nutrient signaling, lipid metabolism, oxidoreductase activity, and ion transport, with several fungal-responsive lncRNAs predicted to act as target mimics for *miR395*, *miR397*, and *miR399* families (Han et al., 2019), while colonization of barley by *Piriformospora indica* triggered extensive lncRNA-miRNA reprogramming linked to auxin signaling, stress adaptation, cell division, and photosynthesis (L. Li et al., 2023). These findings suggest that microbial partners may influence plant responses by reshaping post-transcriptional regulatory networks rather than solely activating individual stress-related genes.

Evidence for microbiome-regulated lncRNA networks under abiotic stress is also beginning to emerge. In Arabidopsis, *Bacillus amyloliquifaciens* LZ04 improved tolerance to calcium stress through activation of an lncRNA-miRNA-mRNA regulatory network controlling stress-responsive genes (F. Li et al., 2020). Although direct mechanistic evidence linking microbiome-induced lncRNAs to drought tolerance in cereals remains scarce, existing studies point to lncRNA-mediated regulation as a potentially important interface between microbial colonization and host stress adaptation. From a holobiont perspective, microbial regulation of lncRNA-miRNA networks may represent an additional layer through which root microbiomes coordinate hormonal, developmental, and stress-responsive pathways under drought.

5. Concluding remarks and future perspectives

Drought resilience in cereals increasingly appears to emerge not from plant responses alone, but from coordinated interactions between host plants and their root-associated microbiomes. Across evolutionary, ecological, genomic, and regulatory dimensions, growing evidence supports the view that root microbiomes can function as extensions of the cereal stress-response system. Beneficial microbial partners reinforce drought adaptation by reshaping host metabolism, regulatory networks, and developmental plasticity across multiple biological levels. These findings further suggest that microbiome-mediated drought tolerance arises through systems-level reconfiguration of host responses rather than activation of isolated stress pathways. This supports a conceptual shift from viewing drought tolerance as an exclusively plant-derived trait toward understanding it as an emergent property of the cereal holobiont.

Despite substantial progress, the mechanistic understanding of microbiome-mediated drought resilience remains limited. Much of the current evidence is still based on correlations between microbial enrichment and improved host performance, making causal relationships difficult to establish. Future research should therefore prioritize experimentally tractable systems combining SynComs, targeted microbial perturbation, functional genomics, and mutant validation to disentangle how specific microbial taxa and signaling pathways contribute to drought adaptation. In this context, microbiome-informed SynComs hold considerable promise not only as candidate bioinoculants for rhizosphere engineering (Qi et al., 2022; Yue et al., 2024), but also as powerful platforms for dissecting signaling mechanisms operating at the root-microbiome interface (Escudero-Martinez et al., 2022; Y. Wang et al., 2022).

Another major challenge concerns the context dependency of microbiome-mediated drought responses. Host genotype, soil

properties, environmental conditions, drought severity, and microbiome composition all influence microbial establishment and functional outcomes (Elango et al., 2025b; Gholizadeh et al., 2022, 2024). This context dependency continues to constrain reproducibility and predictive deployment of microbial strategies across agricultural systems. Integrative approaches combining comparative genomics, metatranscriptomics, metabolomics, epigenomics, and high-resolution functional validation under controlled microbial inoculation will therefore be essential for distinguishing causally relevant microbial functions from secondary or context-specific responses.

Recent conceptual and technological advances may substantially improve both the mechanistic understanding and practical application of microbiome-mediated drought resilience in cereals. Beyond classical phytohormone signaling, increasing attention should be directed toward underexplored regulatory layers, including BR and SL signaling, microbial modulation of SSPs, miRNA-mediated communication, lncRNA-miRNA regulatory networks, and microbiome-associated epigenetic remodeling. However, progress in these areas remains constrained by major technological limitations. For example, the discovery and functional characterization of SSPs and microproteins continue to be hindered by their small size, low abundance, and transient accumulation (Wang et al., 2020), emphasizing the need for more sensitive peptidomics platforms, improved small-protein sequencing pipelines, and high-resolution proteomic infrastructure for cereal-microbiome systems.

Beyond microbial inoculation itself, future rhizosphere engineering may increasingly rely on targeted manipulation of molecular signals that coordinate plant-microbiome interactions. Recent studies showing that rhizosphere-associated plant miRNAs can influence bacterial gene expression raise the possibility of engineering drought-responsive microbiomes through artificial miRNAs or microbial modulation of host post-transcriptional networks (Middleton et al., 2024). Likewise, microbial peptide mimics and SSP-mediated signaling may provide new opportunities to shape microbial recruitment, symbiotic stability, and stress adaptation (Tan et al., 2024). These advances suggest that signaling molecules themselves may become actionable targets for rhizosphere engineering rather than merely passive markers of plant responses.

The emerging role of microbial metabolites in epigenetic regulation offers another promising avenue for durable drought adaptation. Recent evidence showing that microbial-associated metabolites can reshape chromatin accessibility and histone acetylation states highlights the possibility of manipulating rhizosphere conditions to induce more stable stress-responsive phenotypes (Chen et al., 2025). Such approaches may eventually enable microbiome-assisted epigenetic priming strategies capable of reinforcing drought resilience beyond immediate stress exposure.

From a translational perspective, major challenges still limit the field deployment of microbiome-based strategies. Beneficial microbes frequently show inconsistent performance under agricultural conditions due to environmental heterogeneity, unstable colonization, and competition with native microbiota (Moreira et al., 2023). Improving inoculant persistence through advanced formulations, encapsulation technologies, and functionally complementary SynComs will therefore be essential. More broadly, future cereal improvement may increasingly adopt principles analogous to precision therapeutic approaches in medicine, where targeted manipulation of signaling hubs, rather than broad interventions, is used to optimize adaptive outcomes. In this context, integrating microbiome engineering, genome editing, and microbiome-informed breeding strategies may enable the development of cereals optimized not only for plant performance but also for productive interactions within the cereal holobiont.

Ultimately, embracing a holobiont-oriented perspective, in which cereals and their microbiomes are viewed as integrated adaptive systems, may redefine how drought resilience is conceptualized and engineered in sustainable agricultural systems.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

The first author designed and wrote the manuscript under the supervision of Professor Mogens Nicolaisen and Dr. Dinakaran Elango. Other authors reviewed, commented, and approved the manuscript. The figures were designed by Iman Nematy and Hossein Gholizadeh and created with BioRender (BioRender.com).

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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